

Editorial

Analysis of the Emotional and Psychological Health of the Nigerian Military During COVID-19

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Analysis of the Emotional and Psychological Health of the Nigerian Military During COVID-19

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Abstract: This article considers the analysis of the effect COVID-19 had on Nigerian military personnel in terms of their psychological and emotional well-being. It identifies the reasons why outside there; the military personnel are termed rich which causes them to be a low priority during the era of COVID-19. Such affected them psychologically and emotionally. The methodology for the study revolves around the hybrid of questionnaires and interviews. Primary data coming from the methodology employed were analyzed and to consolidate responses from questionnaires, stakeholders considered relevant to the study were interviewed. Results analysis was carried out, using Microsoft Power Business Intelligence software. The study's major finding revealed that despite the work-at-home policies occasioned by the COVID-19 phenomenon, the Nigerian Military was still going to work making them more vulnerable to COVID-19 infection. The study also found out that the distribution of COVID-19 relief was given more to the Non-military than the Military which exacerbated negative emotional and psychological effects on them. Despondently, the Nigerian military was considered as being rich and this led to less than satisfactory attention on mitigating the effect of COVID-19 on them despite their unrelenting efforts in keeping the peace of the country. Based on the findings of this study, the study concludes that the Nigerian Military should be considered for better attention in the event of a pandemic such as COVID-19 for the sake of their psychological and emotional stability.

Key Words: Nigerian Military, COVID-19, Psychology, Emotional, Power BI

I. INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 began towards the end of the year 2019, and according to the World Health Organization, it is a communicable disease that can be fatal (Castelnuovo *et al.*, 2020). No doubt, everybody's life became extremely tense as a result, and fear of death grew among all irrespective of one social or health status. Daily increases in the pandemic's transmission rate were accompanied by a rise in the number of reported fatalities. This accelerated the rate at which people were more frightened while compelling the majority to follow the instructions provided by (Güner *et al.*, 2020) the health professional on safety measures. In this instance, many were psychologically affected. While the goal of psychology is to understand how the mind works. An effective technique to determine if someone has a mental disease is to conduct a psychological examination of them. COVID-19 was a part of the psychological and mental distress that people experienced. This among others is because keeping people in one place for an extended time could cause some detrimental psychological issues, which can cause some people to lose their temper easily, become confused, experience post-traumatic stress, fear contracting

an infection, become bored and become frustrated (Bonati *et al.*, 2022). While an individual's emotions are influenced by the circumstances in which they are found. People's emotional reactions to the pandemic experience may have harmed a variety of people, including sleep issues, unwarranted anxiety, and other issues (Bera *et al.*, 2022). Similarly, some health challenges like obesity were acquired by people during the era of COVID-19 because it promoted some characteristics like eating too much and drinking too much and all these made the emotion of people to be worsened (Burnatowska *et al.*, 2022). This has shown that people suffered emotionally during the period of COVID-19. Some people were able to emotionally handle all of this, but others were not able to, which might have led to the death of some of them. To lessen the adverse effects of the stay-at-home regulations implemented by the majority of governments, including the Nigerian government, individuals and various bodies distributed relief materials to the populace. These materials allowed people to support themselves since they were unable to go out and earn a living for themselves. Here, money, food, soft drinks, and medical kits for COVID-19 were among the relieving goods that were distributed during the event (Ufua *et al.*, 2021).

Although, these kinds of gestures were generally heard especially on social media; this research wasn't able to see any records that pointed to palliative being distributed to Nigerian Military Officers. Since there was little to no research done to determine whether COVID-19 had an impact on the military, it was evident that the military may have been less focused and may not have even believed that they could be influenced (Wynn *et al.*, 2020). Consequently, the Nigerian military risks their life and leaves their loved ones behind to safeguard the countries and the people of Nigeria. Because Nigerian military personnel are also human, it's crucial to understand that they have the same needs as Nigerian civilians (Brouzos *et al.*, 2021).

Most research done on the effects of COVID-19 on the health of people was mainly done using the public, healthcare practitioners, less privileged, and so on but little or no right has been given to see the effect that COVID-19 had on the psychology and the emotions of the Nigerian Military. The study is out to interrogate the welfare effect of psychological and emotionally feeling of the military in the wake of COVID-19. Every effect stated earlier also applies to the Nigerian Military; if care is not taken, it may be more than that. Consequently, it has become important to analyze the effect that COVID-19 had on the Nigerian military by looking at it from the perspective of Nigerian Civilian to be able to see what the Civilians thinks about the Military in other to educate the public to give adequate support to the Nigerian Military in situations that the public was during

COVID-19.

The rest of this research work is as follows: Section 2 is a brief discussion of the past research that was already made. Section 3 explains the material and methods that were used in this research work. Section 4 is the test implementation and necessary discussions are made. The conclusion and future work are discussed in Section 5.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ammar *et al.* (2020) conducted a survey using seven languages to give clarity on the effects the restrictions that were put in place by the Government during COVID-19 had on the psychology and emotions of people. The method that was used by the authors is an online survey that was built using Google. This method used by the authors was used by us too because it became easier to reach a large number of people without seeing them physically. The only thing we finetuned to this method is that we didn't leave the filling of the Google form to the people, technical support was given to the ones that it became difficult for them to fill due to literacy issues and busy schedules. Also, the authors made their case study to fill the survey unlike us where we chose a sample size of people that were closely related or stayed closer to where the Military personnel stays. Due to military rules, it was difficult to survey the military personnel, we had to ask those that interacted with them to fill out the survey on their behalf. The authors' survey was extended to more than three countries making them have a larger dataset that was used for analysis and was able to get a result of the symptoms of depression from the respondents.

Olaseni *et al.* (2020) did about two similar studies where the statistical analysis of the psychological issues faced by Nigerians during COVID-19. The authors used a sample size of 502 Nigerians and were able to list out the different categories and levels of each of the psychological issues on the sample size and the study were able to conclude that Nigerians went through distress during COVID-19. The study didn't state if the survey was conducted with the civilian and the military, so we were forced to conclude that the result of the study spoke for both (Olaseni *et al.*, 2020). We could say of the truth that the Nigerian Military also went through distress during COVID-19.

Considering the study by (Kwaghe *et al.*, 2021), the fact that the health workers in Nigeria were affected both physically and psychologically during COVID-19 was established since they were involved in the care of people during COVID-19. The method used for this study is an interview and qualitative analysis was performed on the dataset. The result from the study was able to identify that part of what the health workers went through during COVID-19 was related to psychology and emotions. We could say that the sample size got into a such mental state because they served humanity. Using the same method of data analysis, can relate this experience to that of the Nigerian Military which despite the risky part of the job, the era of COVID-19 brought mental issues to them.

Nwafor *et al.* (2021) focused their study on pregnant women and used a sample size of 456 pregnant women which was analysed statistically. This shows that different groups of individuals got issues related to mental health during COVID-19. On the other hand, Ogbole *et al.* (2020)

statistically analyzed how the military perceived COVID-19 during the era using a sample size of 216. The study was able to directly collect data from the Nigerian Military which made it easier for them to do the analysis, but the study didn't go into how the Nigerian Military was psychologically and emotionally affected during COVID-19.

In the study conducted by Uford *et al.* (2022), Power BI was part of the tools that were used in the analysis. Power BI was used for the demographic data which showed the beauty of visualization of data using Power BI. Many of these reviewed publications focused on different individual civilian groups and other things, but none focused on the analysis of the psychological and emotional effects of COVID-19 on Nigerian Military personnel.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The method that was used in this research paper is the survey which involves the use of interviews and questionnaires as a means of gathering data (Esiefarienrhe & Mokeresete, 2022). There was no multiple-choice question in the survey but comprises 19 option-choice questions that permit only one answer for each specific question. The option-choice questions comprise some set of questions that were used to collect the demographic of the respondents to know details like the age range, the gender, and the likes. The other details that were also used in the option-choice questions are to know from the respondents' side of view the most populated between the military and the civilian. Also, to know the most populated Military force in Nigeria. We chose to also know if the respondent is a health worker or not. To also know what the civilians think about the income of the military, there was a question to know between the military and the civilian which of them were well paid by the Government. The last set of this category of question dived into asking if the military were affected by COVID-19 if they received and relieved materials, if there were psychological and emotional support from the Government and/or others put in place for the military, to know if there were measures put in place to combat stress for the military, if it was observed that parts of the COVID-19 recorded cases were also from the military, as one of the symptoms of psychological disorder we asked if the military were observed to be tired of their job during COVID-19 due to the stress the went through and been more exposed as they were still meant to go to work despite the stay at home rules by the Government and to also know if people were scared of going closer to the military during COVID-19 in which such could affect their mental health.

The open-ended questions that were in the survey were 9 questions. We chose to know the tribe of the respondent as it couldn't capture all the tribes for such a question to be an option-choice question. We allowed the respondent to enter the health challenges that they had for those that were selected to have any health challenges. We also needed to know the psychological and emotional state of the respondent, we asked to know if they were tested to have any and if they were to state such. We asked the respondent to state the psychological and emotional possible symptoms that they might have observed from the military during COVID-19. We asked the respondent to list the necessary measures that might have been provided to the military to combat stress and some other issues which might lead to psychological and emotional illness. The respondent was to

list what they observed about the precious things the military personnel might have lost during COVID-19. We also asked the respondents to advise to avoid military personnel having psychological and emotional issues.

The military men in Nigeria were to be used for this study, but it was restricted by stringent military regulations that had to be followed. Oyo State and Benue State were the two places we chose to conduct this investigation. This selection of both states was done based on the accessibility. To participate in the study, we selected persons who lived nearby the barracks or were closely related to the Nigerian military troops. We emailed a Google form link with questions that were created with the objective in mind to the respondents who were computer competent. Similarly, to this, those who needed assistance filling out the form were given people to assist them. The questionnaires were distributed by employing a Random sampling technique and the total number of the sample chosen was 500 respondents where 250 for Oyo State and 250 for Benue State. The survey was completed by 477 respondents in total where 280 from Oyo State and 197 from Benue State.

Before finally sending out the questionnaires, we had some selected people that we sent questionnaires to which made two of them volunteer to be interviewed. One had close relations with military personnel and the other was married to the military personnel. They booked an appointment for the interviews which were conducted using WhatsApp voice call and also messages (chats) with voice messages. The first interview lasted for more than one hour as the research got the interviewee to be much interested. The second interview took about 20 minutes. The interest they both developed made it easier for open-ended questions to be asked as they also promised to fill out the questionnaires. The interview made us restructure the questions in the questionnaires as it opened our eyes to some missing important aspects that we needed to consider.

We went through the responses gotten from the questionnaires to see if there were missing values and we noticed there were no missing values as there were validation tools on Google form which made the important fields be filled by the respondent. And those that filled themselves were literates in a task as such. The others were supported by the team members. It became easier for us to begin with the analysis of the dataset after the dataset was downloaded from the online Google Drive.

Since the responses were both in quantitative and qualitative form, we chose to use Microsoft Power Business Intelligence tool for the analysis of the dataset. For the qualitative analysis, the responses were text-based. That is, they were in sentences. The tool that is used for theming related words in Power BI was used in the analysis and visualization of them. The quantitative part of the dataset was visualized and analyzed using the various tools that Power BI has for such analysis.

Microsoft Power BI was chosen for the analysis of the dataset because it is a powerful tool for analysis and because of its ease of use for the analysis of the text. It was an easy tool for us since it is one of the popular tools, it can also be used for the analysis of any size of data and ease of understanding of insights by anyone irrespective of literacy level.

As the responses kept coming, we could follow as it was going because of the automated visualizing tool that Power BI has. We kept on monitoring the responses and seeing the different trends of the dataset. The richness of the dashboard in Power BI helps in having instant answers and it helped us to work locally and remotely. For the quantitative analysis, the responses that were not numeric were made numeric like using 1 for Yes, 0 for No, and 2 for Maybe.

Microsoft Power BI became a good tool for us as it was easier for us to use and learn within a few days for those with no prior knowledge of the user because it doesn't require knowledge of programming as the few codes that were written were less and was used in calculation of percentages which aid our analysis of the datasets. There was also an instant feel of activities when using tools that are used for click-and-drop or click-and-apply. This helped us to follow through during the design of the reports on the dashboard. The image below is the sample of the questionnaire that was used for data collection.

ANALYSIS OF THE EMOTIONAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF THE NIGERIAN MILITARY DURING COVID 19

Hi there, I'm Christianah Titilope Ojewale a Masters student of University of Ibadan. I'm conducting a research on the above topic. Thank you for helping out in filling the questionnaire.

Despite the sit at home law that was passed during Covid-19, there were still additional duties for the military personnel to ensure that the laws were obeyed. There were no record if they were properly taken care of during the pandemic. This project aimed at analyzing if what the military went through during the Covid-19 period had emotional and psychological effects on them.

Please be transparent as much as possible.

NOTE: Details about your identity are not required in this questionnaire. A particular response won't be traced to any respondent.

oyewalechristianah@ttitilope@gmail.com (not shared) [Switch accounts](#)

*Required

1. Which age range do you belong to? *

Below 20

21 - 30

31-40

41-50

50 and above

2. What is your gender? *

Male

Female

I choose not to answer

3. What is your religion? *

Christianity

Figure 1: Image of the Questionnaire Used for Data Collection

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As explained previously, the case study that we used in this research work was people that had close interaction with Nigerian Military personnel. After the proper formatting of

other to show them that they were also loved by the Government.

V. CONCLUSION

The focus of this study is on the analyses of the psychological and emotional effects of COVID-19 on Nigerian military personnel. The perverse nature of the effect of COVID-19 and the desire to interrogate how the pandemic affected the Nigerian military personnel psychologically and emotionally provided the motivation for the study. Granted that the government of the Federal of Nigeria deployed a wide range of palliative measures to address the pandemic to different sets of the people of Nigeria; the way and nature of palliatives channelled to the Nigerian military personnel as one of the highly vulnerable groups of people to the pandemic generated interesting findings. Hence, information was clustered from close relatives and interested members of the military community. With the hybrid, that is, a combination of questionnaire and transcribed interview data, the study generated a dataset that revealed the gender mix of the relatives of the Nigerian military personnel; the profile of palliative measures channelled to the Nigerian military personnel, and the extent of monetary compensation given to the Nigerian military person to cushion the effect of COVID-19 pandemic, the study found out that the Nigerian Military personnel were excluded from palliative interventions embarked upon by the Government. This finding invariably indicated that the Nigerian military personnel did not enjoy the appropriate volume of palliatives despite the high-risk nature of the works of military personnel during the COVID-19 era. To this effect, the observed neglect of the Nigerian military personnel adversely affected them psychologically and emotionally as respondents with different age categorizations maintained that the psychological and emotional being of the Nigerian military personnel was not taken care of. This finding appears unsatisfactory given the security services that Nigerian military personnel are assigned to perform with or without any pandemic. Thus, with this major finding, the study has revealed the need to address the abnormality inherent in the distribution of COVID-19 palliative measures by allowing such measures in the form of interventions meant to mitigate psychological and emotional adverse effects of any pandemics such as COVID-19 to flow to the Nigerian military personnel for the sake of their welfare consideration.

REFERENCES

- Ammar, A., Mueller, P., Trabelsi, K., Chtourou, H., Boukhris, O., Masmoudi, L., Bouaziz, B., Brach, M., Schmicker, M., Bentlage, E., How, D., Ahmed, M., Aloui, A., Hammouda, O., Paineiras-Domingos, L. L., Braakmanjansen, A., Wrede, C., Bastoni, S., Pernambuco, C. S., ... Hoekelmann, A. (2020). Psychological consequences of COVID-19 home confinement: The ECLB-COVID19 multicenter study. *PLoS ONE*, *15*(11), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0240204>
- Bera, L., Souchon, M., Ladsous, A., Colin, V., & Lopez-Castroman, J. (2022). Emotional and behavioral impact of the COVID-19 epidemic in adolescents. *Current Psychiatry Reports*, *24*(1), 37–46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11920-022-01313-8>
- Bonati, M., Campi, R., & Segre, G. (2022). Psychological impact of the quarantine during the COVID-19 pandemic on the general European adult population: A systematic review of the evidence. *Epidemiology and Psychiatric Sciences*, *31*(e27), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S2045796022000051>
- Brouzos, A., Vassilopoulos, S. P., Baourda, V. C., Tassi, C., Stavrou, V., Moschou, K., & Brouzou, K. O. (2021). “Staying Home – Feeling Positive”: Effectiveness of an on-line positive psychology group intervention during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Current Psychology*, *42*(4), 2749–2761. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-01613-x>
- Burnatowska, E., Surma, S., & Olszanecka-Glinianowicz, M. (2022). Relationship between mental health and emotional eating during the COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic review. *Nutrients*, *14*(19), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14193989>
- Castelnuovo, G., De Giorgio, A., Manzoni, G. M., Treadway, D. C., & Mohiyeddini, C. (2020). Psychological, behavioral, and interpersonal effects and clinical implications for health systems of the Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic: A call for research. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *11*, 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.02146>
- Esiefarienrhe, B. M., & Mokeresete, M. (2022). Using software applications to enhance e-government service delivery in Botswana. *Journal of Information Systems and Informatics*, *4*(3), 495–510. <https://doi.org/10.51519/journalisi.v4i3.262>
- Güner, R., Hasanoğlu, İ., & Aktaş, F. (2020). COVID-19: Prevention and control measures in community. *Turkish Journal of Medical Sciences*, *50*(9), 571–577. <https://doi.org/10.3906/sag-2004-146>
- Kwaghe, A. V., Kwaghe, V. G., Habib, Z. G., Kwaghe, G. V., Ilesanmi, O. S., Ekele, B. A., Umeokonkwo, C. D., & Balogun, M. S. (2021). Stigmatization and psychological impact of COVID-19 pandemic on frontline healthcare Workers in Nigeria: A qualitative study. *BMC Psychiatry*, *21*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-021-03540-4>
- Nwafor, J. I., Okedo-Alex, I. N., & Ikeotuonye, A. C. (2021). Prevalence and predictors of depression, anxiety, and stress symptoms among pregnant women during COVID-19-related lockdown in Abakaliki, Nigeria. *Malawi Medical Journal*, *33*(1), 54–58. <https://doi.org/10.4314/mmj.v33i1.8>
- Ogbole, A. J., Bisji, J. S., Umar, S. J., Jallo, I. M., Ezeh, S. O., & James, A. L. (2020). Knowledge, attitudes and perception in regard to COVID-19 pandemic in Nigerian military population. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, *7*(11), 231–249. <https://doi.org/10.14738/assrj.711.9254>
- Olaseni, A. O., Akinsola, O. S., Agberotimi, S. F., & Oguntayo, R. (2020). Psychological distress experiences of Nigerians during COVID-19 pandemic; the gender difference. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, *2*(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2020.100052>
- Uford, I., Charles, I., & Ekong, J. E. (2022). The COVID-19 crisis and regular telework: The effect of stress on the Nigerian oil and gas employees’ work perception. *European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, *7*(2), 179–199. <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejmms.v7i2.1252>
- Ufua, D. E., Osabuohien, E., Ogbari, M. E., Falola, H. O., Okoh, E. E., & Lakhani, A. (2021). Re-strategising

Government palliative support systems in tackling the challenges of COVID-19 lockdown in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management*, 22(1), S19–S32.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40171-021-00263-z>

Wynn, G., Morganstein, J. C., Jetly, R., Ford, S. C., Vance,

M. C., Meyer, E. G., West, J. C., Benedek, D. M., & Ursano, R. J. (2020). Military mental health and COVID-19. *Journal of Military, Veteran and Family Health*, 6(S2), 21–26. <https://doi.org/10.3138/jmvfh-2020-0048>